

Learning System of Islamic Religious Education

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Abstract

Humans as creatures created by Allah SWT have been given extraordinary potential in the form of perfect physical and spiritual. Human perfection is more complete and complete with the addition of reason. With this potential, humans develop themselves to utilize all these potentials until they reach the degree of human perfection. However, human perfection can be lowered in degree, even lower than the level of animals if humans are not able to maintain that perfection. In order to keep the degree of humans not lower than the degrees of animals, humans must understand, maintain and develop their nature through education. Armed with this potential, humans are given the freedom to determine their life path, whether to choose the path of goodness or choose the path of evil. Later in front of Allah, for this choice, humans will be held accountable. However, for all of God's mercy and love for humans, he was not allowed to just choose his life path, but Allah sent down the Qur'an as a guide and source of knowledge as a provision to achieve happiness in this world and the hereafter. The ultimate goal of man in Islam is what can also be called the ultimate goal of Islamic education.

Keywords: *Learning System, Islamic Religious Education*

A. Introduction

Humans as creatures created by Allah SWT have been given extraordinary potential in the form of perfect physical and spiritual. Human perfection is more complete and complete with the addition of reason. With this potential, humans develop themselves to utilize all these potentials until they reach the degree of human perfection. Strictly and clearly Allah SWT states the perfection of human creation as he said in the Qur'an Surah At-Tin verse 4: "*Indeed We have created man in the best form*". However, human perfection can be lowered in degree, even lower than the level of animals if humans are not able to maintain that perfection. "*Then We returned him to the lowest possible place*" (Surah At-Tin: 5). In order to keep the degree of humans not lower than the degrees of animals, humans must understand, maintain and develop their nature through education. Armed with this potential, humans are given the freedom to determine their life path, whether to choose the path of goodness or choose the path of evil. Later in front of Allah SWT, for this choice, humans will be held accountable. However, for all of God's mercy and love for humans, he was not allowed to just choose his life path, but Allah SWT sent down the Qur'an as a guide and source of knowledge as a provision to achieve happiness in this world and the hereafter.

Islamic education is only one aspect of the overall teachings of Islam. Therefore, the purpose of Islamic education cannot be separated from the purpose of human life in Islam; namely creating a personal servant of Allah SWT who fears Him, and can achieve happiness in life in this world and in the hereafter. The ultimate goal of man in Islam is what can be called the ultimate goal of Islamic education. Then, how to reach the goal of human life? So Allah SWT sent down the Qur'an as a guide and a source to be studied through education and then practiced in everyday life.

Islamic education is essentially an educational process based on Islamic values as included in the Qur'an and the Prophet's Hadits. That is why it is very important to explore theoretical conceptions of education as contained in the Qur'an and Hadith. This simple paper intends to describe the nature of the Islamic education system as ordered in the Qur'an and Hadits. In brief, this paper will explain what the essence of the Islamic education system is, its basis and objectives, and the function of Islamic education.

B. Explanation

1. The Definition of Islamic Religious Education

The word education in the Qur'an, as expressed by many scholars and writers, is a derivation of several words, namely from the word al-tarbiyah derived from the word rabiya, yarba which means nasya'a and tara'ra'a, which means nasya'a means to grow, thrive, and develop. This is in line with the word of God in the Qur'an: *"God destroys usury and enriches alms. And Allah SWT does not like anyone who remains in disbelief, and always commits sin"* (Surah Al-Baqarah, 2: 276)

With this linguistic understanding, the word al-tarbiyah or education is a term related to efforts to grow or explore all physical, psychological, talents, interests, talents and various other skills possessed by humans, or actualize various hidden human potentials, then develop them by caring for and nurturing it with love.

Departing from the etymological notion of education as described above, Achmadi definitively states that what is meant by the notion of Islamic education is all efforts to maintain and develop human nature and the human resources available to it towards the formation of a complete human being (insan kamil) in accordance with Islamic norms.

Islamic Religious Education is an educational system in which Islamic ideology sourced from the Qur'an and Sunnah becomes the main basis in the educational process as an

effort to form Islamic individuals and communities and make Islamic teachings a way of life for the safety and welfare of life in the world and in the world hereafter.

2. Learning System of Islamic Religious Education

The system is a unit consisting of components or elements that interact, are interrelated, or depend on each other to form a complex whole. In Law No. 20 of 2003 concerning the national education system, it is stated that national education functions to develop capabilities and shape the character and civilization of a dignified nation in the context of educating the nation's life, aiming to develop the potential of students to become human beings who believe and fear God Almighty. Almighty, noble, healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, and become a democratic and responsible citizen.

The national education system does not actually nominate the Indonesian Islamic education system, and the meaning of the whole human being in the goals of national education through various types, levels, nature and forms of education/training as a humanitarian process that acts in logical thinking as intelligent and virtuous beings, as well as a humanitarian process who are able to carry out their main duties and functions fully, who hold a divine mandate which refers to their relationship with God along with the desired behavior in it and a cultural mandate that contains the meaning of being a cultured human being. Indonesia, although it is expressly stated that it is neither a religious state nor a secular state, but a Pancasila state.

According to Bahtiar Effendi, the Pancasila State, it can be said that Indonesia takes the middle path between a religious state and a secular state. The formulation of the first precepts of Pancasila and Article 29 of the 1945 Constitution Paragraph (1) gives a unique characteristic to the State of Indonesia, not a secular state that separates religion and the state, and not a religious state based on a particular religion. The Pancasila state

guarantees the freedom of every citizen to have religion and is obliged to maintain noble character based on the values of Pancasila. Philosophically, the nation's view of life does not conflict with Islamic teachings, so Indonesian Islamic education should be able to become a sub-system of national education.

Especially since the issuance of the UUSPN Number 2 of 1989 and the 2003 National Education Bill, which are future-minded and the introduction of the link and match policy in education, is an opportunity as well as a challenge for Islamic education systems and institutions, especially for Muslim scholars and scholars to formulate designs as well as pioneering Islamic education building that has a future perspective, in accordance with the basic mission of the word Al-Islam, is Islamizing which means carrying out education in accordance with Islamic needs and dynamics.

There are three important things that are characteristic of a system. First, every system has a purpose. Purpose is the main characteristic of a system. Second, the system always contains a process. The process is a series of activities directed towards achieving goals. Third, the process of activities in a system always involves and utilizes various components or certain elements. So the system requires mutual support.

A learning system, especially Islamic education, is a unit of learning components which include objectives, materials, methods, media, curriculum, and evaluation. In order to achieve the goals of Islamic education itself, namely to create generations of believers, morals and broad knowledge, or it can be interpreted as an effort to link and function the elements that exist in the learning process of Islamic education to achieve the stated goals. The components of the learning system can be described by the following learning process scheme:

1. Learning Objectives of Islamic Religious Education

The first and main component the learning objectives of Islamic education are in line with the objectives of the mission of Islam itself, namely increasing and enhancing moral values, so as to reach the level of al-karimah morality (Asy-Syaibany, 1979), these goals are the same and congruent with the target set contained in the prophetic task carried out by Rasulullah SAW, which was revealed in his statement "*Indeed I was sent to guide people to achieve noble character*" (al-Hadits).

Islam as a divine constitution has provided a complete law on human life, is universal, its validity is not limited by space and time. Therefore, Islam always pays attention to culture and does not reject tajdid, so that Islamic education can be directed to two goals:

a. The Main Purpose

The main purpose are goals that must be achieved by the Islamic education system according to the source and basis of its implementation, without limitations of space and time Prof. Moh. Athiyah al-Abraisy concluded that there are five goals of Islamic education:

- 1) Helping the formation of noble character
- 2) Prepare for the life of this world and the hereafter
- 3) Forming a complete person, physically and mentally healthy
- 4) Cultivating a scientific spirit, allowing students to study knowledge for the sake of science itself.
- 5) Prepare students to be able to carry out worldly tasks well or in short preparation to seek sustenance.

From the formulation of the goals of Islamic education in general above, it can be simplified that in the end the goal of Islamic education is to form human beings with Muslim

personalities, namely humans who are pious, truly pious to Allah SWT. This is in accordance with the verse:

يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا اتَّقُوا اللَّهَ حَقَّ تَقَاتِهِ وَلَا تَمُوتُنَّ إِلَّا وَأَنْتُمْ مُسْلِمُونَ

Meaning: "Oh you who believe, fear Allah SWT, truly fear, and do not ever die except in a state of Islam" (Q.S. Ali Imaran: 102)

b. The Specific Purpose

The specific purpose pay more attention to, emphasize and demand students to have certain understandings, abilities and skills that lead to the realization of the goals of Islamic education in general, and are adapted to the existing education level. For example, piety, as indicators include prayer, zakat, fasting, and hajj, so in basic education, students are required to be able to pray, zakat, fast during the holy month of Ramadan and practice the procedures for the pilgrimage. The directions of Islamic education are:

- 1) The formation of a noble character
- 2) Strong aqidah (faith) and piety
- 3) High Islamic image of human relations

3. Islamic Religious Education Learning Material

Muslim education experts emphasize that there is a close relationship between the intellectual potential of students and the scientific material taught to them. Ibn Jama'ah reminded teachers about their obligation to provide and detail the material presented, so that it is easily understood by students. And this is the example shown by the Prophet, "his speech is so detailed and clear, so that the listener can easily understand it. When he said important words he repeated three times to be understood and when he finished discussing a problem, he stopped for a moment to give other people the opportunity to ask questions and speak,"

said Ibn Jama'ah in *Tadzkirat al-Sami'*. So that a teacher must carefully prepare activities in the teaching and learning process, by choosing the material to be presented to students based on the subject matter guidelines that have been stated in the GPP (Outlines of the Education Program). must :

a. Over matter

b. Plan activities, which include:

- 1) Description of the subject
- 2) Determine the approach and selection of teaching methods
- 3) Determine learning facilities and resources
- 4) Determine the time allocation
- 5) Make evaluation

So what is contained in Islamic religious education learning materials, of course, are components of the field of Islamic religious education studies, which consist of the Qur'an and Hadith, Fiqh, Aqidah, Morals, and Islamic history.

a. Method

The teaching method is a technique of delivering lesson materials to students. It is intended so that students can catch lessons easily, effectively and can be accepted by students well. There are various methods that can be taken by teachers in delivering lessons, including:

a. Lecture method

Is a method of *mau'idhoh hasanah* with an oral bill in order to receive good advice or education. As did the Prophet Muhammad SAW to his people. That is to believe in Allah SWT and Rasulullah SAW.

b. Question and answer method

Is a learning method that aims to make students have the ability to think and can describe knowledge that ranks at the level of brain intelligence and intellect.

c. Sociodrama Method

Is a teaching method that is carried out by portraying the characters who want to be conveyed according to the material, or commonly used in the subject, such as school customs, ta'ziah, and others.

e. Study Tour Method

The teaching method is by inviting students to visit an object in order to expand their knowledge and then students make reports and discuss them and record the results of the visit accompanied by educators. For example, visiting the market to find out the practice of buying and selling in Fiqh material.

4. Islamic Religious Education Learning Media

Learning media for religious education is anything that can be used to channel religious education messages from the sender or teacher to the recipient (student) and can stimulate the thoughts, feelings, concerns and interests and concerns of students so that the teaching and learning process of education occurs. Hamalik stated as quoted by Azhar Irsyad that "the use of teaching media in the teaching and learning process can generate new desires and interests, generate motivation, and stimulate learning activities, and even bring psychological effects on students.

5. Curriculum

The curriculum is a tool to achieve educational goals. Thus, the curriculum is an important tool to achieve goals, the curriculum should play a role and be anticipatory and adaptive to changes and advances in science and technology. Basically, the curriculum is

composed of various main aspects that characterize it. Among the aspects contained in the curriculum are:

- a. The educational goals to be achieved by the curriculum
- b. Knowledge, sciences, data, activities and experiences that are the source of the formation of the curriculum.
- c. Methods and methods of teaching and guidance followed by students to propel them in the direction desired by the designed objectives.
- d. The methods and methods of assessment used in measuring the results of the educational process designed in the curriculum (Hasan Langgulung, 1986).

The educational goals to be achieved by the curriculum in Islamic education are the same as the goals of Islamic education itself, namely forming noble character in relation to the nature of human creation. In this case, then in a broad sense, the Islamic education curriculum contains material for lifelong education, as a realization of the prophet's demands "Seek knowledge from the cradle to the grave" (al-Hadith).

6. Islamic Religious Education Learning Evaluation

Etymologically, evaluation comes from the word "to evaluate" which means "to assess". Evaluation of religious education is an activity to determine the level of progress of a job in religious education. Evaluation is a tool to measure the extent of student mastery of the education that has been given.

Evaluation not only serves to see the success of students in the learning process, but also serves as feedback for teachers on their performance in learning management. Through evaluation we can see the shortcomings in the utilization of various components of the learning system. The targets of the evaluation of Islamic education broadly include four basic human abilities, namely:

- a. Attitudes and experiences towards the meaning of a personal relationship with his god.
- b. Attitudes and experiences towards the meaning of personal relationships with society.
- c. Attitudes and experiences towards the meaning of personal relationships with the natural surroundings.
- d. Attitudes and views towards oneself as a servant of Allah and as a member of the community and as a caliph before the earth. The various types of evaluation of learning outcomes in the teaching and learning process of religious education in schools can be distinguished as follows:

a. Formative Evaluation

Formative evaluation is an evaluation that is carried out after completing one subject. Thus the evaluation of short-term learning outcomes. In its implementation in schools, this formative evaluation is a daily test.

b. Summative Evaluation

Summative evaluation is an evaluation that is carried out after completing several topics. Thus, summative evaluation is an evaluation of long-term learning outcomes. In its implementation in schools, if formative evaluation can be equated with daily tests, then summative evaluations can be likened to general tests which are usually carried out at the end of every chess month or end of semester.

c. Placement Evaluation

If enough prospective students are accepted in a school so that more than one class is needed, then special considerations are needed for distribution. Whether good children will be united in one class or all classes will be filled with a mixture of good, moderate and poor

children, information is needed. Such information can be obtained by means of a placement evaluation. This test is carried out at the beginning of the school year to determine the level of student knowledge related to the material that has been delivered.

d. Diagnostic Evaluation

It is an evaluation that serves to identify the life background (psychological, physical and mental) of students who have learning difficulties whose results can be used as a basis in solving these difficulties.

Conclusion

A learning system, especially Islamic education, is a unit of learning components which include objectives, materials, methods, media, curriculum, and evaluation. In order to achieve the goals of Islamic education itself, namely to create generations of believers, morals and broad knowledge, or it can be interpreted as an effort to link and function the elements that exist in the learning process of Islamic education to achieve the stated goals.

The purpose of learning Islamic education is in line with the objectives of the mission of Islam itself, namely to increase and enhance moral values, so as to achieve the level of moral al-karimah, these goals are the same and congruent with the targets contained in the prophetic duties carried out by Rasulullah SAW, which was revealed in the statement He said, "Indeed, I was sent to guide people to achieve noble character" (al-Hadits).

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